

A STUDY ON MARKET DEMAND AND PREFERENCES FOR SPORTS ACTIVITIES AMONG PREGNANT WOMEN IN BULGARIA

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Abstract

Physical activity during pregnancy is increasingly recognized as a key factor in maintaining women's physical health and psycho-emotional well-being. This study analyzes market demand and preferences for sports services targeting pregnant women in Bulgaria. It examines consumer attitudes regarding the safety, accessibility, and effectiveness of the offered services, as well as the role of sports marketing within the wellness industry. The research highlights the growing economic value of sport and the need for targeted marketing strategies tailored to the specific needs of pregnant women. The findings have practical implications for professionals in the fields of sports and health, as well as for providers of prenatal care services.

Keywords: pregnancy, physical activity, market demand, sports marketing, women's health

Introduction

In today's world, physical activity during pregnancy is recognized as vital for the physical and psycho-emotional well-being of expectant mothers. Studies [1,2] highlight benefits such as improved vitality, reduced risk of gestational diabetes, hypertension, and postpartum depression. This drives a growing interest in specialized sports services for pregnant women.

In Bulgaria, data show trends in consumer attitudes, demand, and satisfaction with these services. The study analyses the market landscape and the preferences of pregnant women regarding safety, accessibility, and effectiveness of sport-related services, offering insights valuable to wellness professionals and prenatal care providers [3,4,5].

The rising demand for physical activity connects sport and the economy. Sport is both a means of achieving health and balance and a dynamic business sector with investment potential [6,7,8]. Its development is supported by economic growth, media influence, and increased funding from governments and corporations, driving modern sports marketing [9,10,11]¹.

Marketing is defined by the American Marketing Association as "the process of planning and executing the conception, pricing, promotion, and distribution of ideas, goods, and services to create exchanges that satisfy individual and organizational objectives." Similarly, CIM defines it as "the management process responsible for identifying, anticipating, and satisfying customer requirements profitably."

Sport cannot be separated from the evolving social and market environment. Sports marketing, as an applied science, is focused on consumer needs and built on the marketing mix: product, pricing, promotion, and distribution, with research as a key element [12,9,13].

Marketing research studies consumer demand, aiming to collect accurate and timely data that can guide product development. Sport services for pregnant women generally resemble other services but are tailored to the specific characteristics of this user group, classified under "sport for all."

The primary orientations of sports services for pregnant women can be categorized as follows:

- *Recreational* – aimed at relieving stress and fostering a more positive attitude toward the new and unfamiliar state that every pregnant woman experiences, particularly during a first pregnancy;
- *Preventive* – focused on minimizing potential complications during the nine months of pregnancy and maintaining general physical fitness;
- *Educational* – supporting women in understanding their own bodies and the physiological changes that occur throughout pregnancy;
- *Therapeutic* – assisting in the management and alleviation of mild health complaints and discomforts resulting from pregnancy.

When examined through the lens of marketing and viewed as a sport-related product (see Fig.1), *sport for pregnant women* falls within the category of *core sport products*, more specifically in the subclass of *sport services (activities)*. According to Y. Kalaikov [12], "A sport service is a primary product within the field of 'sport for all', through which conditions are created for systematic engagement in physical exercise and sport, with the aim of promoting health and improving individuals' physical capacity."

¹ https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/A-7-2012-0388_EN.html

RECREATIONAL SERVICES FOR PREGNANT WOMEN

Figure 1. Recreational Services for Pregnant Women

Methodology

The Bulgarian sport services market offers an increasingly diverse range of motor activities – from individual sessions to group workouts. A notable trend is the rising demand for *specialized services for pregnant women*, reflecting growing public awareness of the benefits of physical activity during pregnancy, similar to trends in Western Europe and the U.S.

In recent years, more providers have emerged to serve this target group. However, unlike in more developed countries, Bulgaria shows a quantitative surplus of services, often at the expense of quality. Effective prenatal sport services require a clear understanding of women's specific needs, preferences, and expectations. Thus, consumer profiling should be central to the marketing strategies of organizations targeting this segment.

Results

In the city of Sofia, approximately 90% of the so-called “*modern schools for pregnant women*” operate primarily within hospital facilities and focus mainly on providing consultative sessions for expectant mothers. These sessions emphasize psychological preparation for childbirth, as well as practical advice related to pregnancy and parenting. However, they do not offer structured physical activity programs (see Figure 2).

It is noteworthy that only 10% of these centers include physical activity as part of their services. The preferred formats include prenatal gymnastics, yoga, Pilates, fitball exercises, and aqua gymnastics. Notable examples of such centers are “*Modern Parents*” and *St. Sofia Hospital* (led by Dr. Mazneikova, Bulgaria), where sessions are conducted by specialists with some training in the field.

The main reasons for limited access to quality motor activity programs include:

Figure 2. Distribution of Schools for Pregnant Women in the City of Sofia According to the Availability of Motor Activity

- *Shortage of qualified personnel* specialized in working with pregnant and postpartum women;
- *Insufficient awareness* of the specific needs and characteristics of this target group;
- *Lack of standardized and evidence-based programs* tailored to the physiological condition of pregnant women.

According to several authors [13,14,15,16], the development of this type of service requires investment in specialist training, the design of appropriate training models, and increased market competition. These factors could significantly improve the quality and safety of sport services for pregnant women.

A major issue in providing sport services for pregnant women is the disconnect between their specific physiological and emotional needs and the commonly applied, standardized approaches, which often neglect individual differences and pregnancy stages. There is a notable lack of qualified specialists, trained to work with pregnant and postpartum women, which may result in the use of unsuitable or non-validated physical activities, sometimes posing health risks. As [17] emphasizes in the context of wellness culture, applying innovative and personalized methodologies is essential for achieving sustainable and safe outcomes in specialized populations. An important exception is the Nesheva Program [18] – a scientifically grounded initiative developed in Bulgaria in 2010 and validated over the past 15 years, offering an evidence-based framework for prenatal physical activity.

Conclusion

The results of the present study demonstrate a growing interest among pregnant women in Bulgaria in engaging in physical activity, with a clear preference for programs tailored to the specific physiological characteristics of pregnancy. At the same time, the analysis of existing services reveals structural deficiencies, including a shortage of qualified specialists and a limited availability of scientifically grounded and individualized programs.

This mismatch between demand and supply underscores the need for the systematic development of specialized physical activity programs for pregnant women, as well as for enhancing the professional expertise of practitioners in the field. To effectively address these challenges, political support, interdisciplinary collaboration, and the integration of evidence-based practices – such as the Nesheva Program (Bulgaria) – are essential. The implementation of targeted training for healthcare and fitness professionals, combined with long-term program validation, can contribute to safer and more beneficial outcomes for both mothers and their unborn children. Meeting these needs is not only a matter of improving service quality, but also of affirming maternal health as a public health priority.

Note:

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References

1. Nesheva, I. (2014). Vliyanie na gimnastikata pri zheni s normalna bremennost. Disertatsia. Sofia, pp.1–186 [in Bulgaria]
2. Kisselkova, E. (2006). Physiological characteristics of sports sessions with women (in Human Physiology with Physiology of Sport), Publ. *House New Knowledge*, Sofia, pp.147-155
3. Angelcheva, M. (2023). Complex SPA program effect on overweight women's physical condition and well-being - *Trakia Journal of Sciences – St. Zagora*, 2023, Vol. 21, (Suppl.1), pp. 556-560, eISSN 1313-3551. (Available from: <http://www.uni-sz.bg/>)
4. Dimitrova, N. (2019). Reactions of the motor system in local and global activities. *Trakia Journal of Sciences*, Vol. 17, (Suppl.1), pp. 635 – 637, doi:10.15547/tjs.2019.s.01.100, (online) Available from: <http://www.uni-sz.bg>, eISSN:1313-3551
5. Popova-Dobrev D. (2023). Health Promotion in Certified SPA and Balneotherapy (Medical SPA) Centres in Stara Zagora Region. *SHS Web of Conferences EDP Sciences*, Vol. 176, (p. 01007), pp.1-5. eISSN: 2261-2424
6. Kalaykov, Y. (2007). Menidzhmant na sporta. Teoretiko-metodologicheski i prilozhni aspekti. Monografia. Izd. NSA Pres, Sofia, pp.1-232, ISBN: 978-954-718-218-9 [in Bulgaria]
7. Tsolov, B. (2002). Reklamata v sporta. *Votomami*, Sofia [in Bulgaria]
8. Draganov, G. (2012). Sistematologichna karakteristika na rabotnicheskia sport v Republika Bulgaria v savremennite sotsialno-ikonomicheski uslovia. *Sport & Nauka*, br. 4 [in Bulgaria]
9. Tsolov, B. (2008). Osnovi na marketinga v sporta. *Bolid-Ins*, Sofia [in Bulgaria]
10. Nashwan, S., M. Ahmed (2024). The Intermediary Role of Electronic Word of Mouth in the Relationship Between Digital Marketing Techniques and Purchasing Behaviour. *Journal of Lifestyle and SDGs Review*, 4(2) (online) doi.org/10.47172/2965-730x.sdgsreview.v4.n02.pe02465
11. Kotler, P., Gary Armstrong, Veronica Wong, John Saunders (2008). *Principles Of Marketing*. Pearson Education Limited, p. 77.
12. Kalaykov, Y. (2009). Terminologia na menidzhmanta v sporta. Izd. NSA Pres, Sofia, p.45, ISBN: 978-954-718-214-1 [in Bulgaria]
13. Dimitrova, B., T. Tomova (2025). A Wellness lifestyle, emotional intelligence, workplace and leadership success. *International Scientific journal Smart Innovations in Recreational, Wellness Industry and Niche Tourism*. Vol. 6 (Iss. 2), pp. 51-56, eISSN 2603-4921 (Available from: <https://scjournal.globalwaterhealth.org/>)
14. Dimitrova, B. (2019). Quality assessment about standards for wellness services and certified skills of specialised staff. (online) doi 10.15547 /

tjs.2019.02.007. Trakia Journal of Sciences – St. Zagora, 17(2), pp. 143-149. Available from: <http://tru.unisz.bg/tsj/Vol.17,%20Suppl.2,%202019/7.pdf>, eISSN: 1313-3551

15. Dimitrova, B. (2019a). New smart educational model "Wellness instructor". Monograph. Ed. Avangard Prima, first edition, Sofia, pp.11-12. ISBN: 978-619-239-150-8.

16. Dimitrova, B., (2023). Educational policy, specialised staff, innovations and recreational industry. Strategies for Policy in Science and Education, 31(5), pp.532-546, <https://doi.org/10.53656/str2023-5-6-imp>.

17. Ignatova, D. (2023). Affirming wellness culture through innovative methodology related to Blaze-pod trainer system, Strategies for policy in science and education, (Online), Sofia, 31 (2), pp. 212-225. <https://doi.org/10.53656/str2023-2-7-aff>, ISSN 1310 – 0270

18. Nesheva I. (2023). Izsledvane efektivnostta na Uelnes (wellness) praktiki pri normalna bremennost. Monografia. Nauchno izdatelstvo NSA Pres, Pechat – Bulged OOD Sofia, s.1-132, ISBN 978-954-718-723-8 [in Bulgaria]